

Marketing Communication Strategy Online Product Cell Phone in Attracting Buyers

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ABSTRACT

Marketing Communication Strategy for a product in a company is a form of marketing improvement strategy in advancing or improving a company or business actor and making the products offered more popular. The theory used in this research is IMC (*Intergrated Marketing Communication*). This type of research uses qualitative research with a case study approach. The data sources used were primary and secondary data sources with a total of 5 informants. The data collection techniques used in this research are observation, interviews and documentation. Research results show that Marketing Communication Strategy Online Product Painful Attracting Buyer Interest is said to be good by referring to indicators (1) Advertising (*Advertising*), where the form of communication is carried out by posting products with photos and descriptions that are clear and easy for buyers to understand, as well as several unique descriptions. Then indicator (2) Sales Promotion (*Sales Promotion*), namely by providing a package *bundling* and *flash sale*. Indicator (3) Public Relations (*Public Relation*), where each member maintains communication by posting information, commenting on photos of other members' products and communicating with customers in the comments column, direct messages and even *whatsapp*. Indicator (4) Individual Sales (*Personal Selling*), namely explaining in language that is easy to understand, providing comments on posts and providing product suggestions if there are customers who are looking for products with *range* price or customer requirements. Indicator (5) Direct Sales (*Direct Selling*), namely communicating with customers who have made several transactions, by offering new or unused products directly through *inbox* or number *whatsapp* which has been saved. Then the supporting factors are the seller's consistency in marketing by posting interesting products and information as well as media reach *facebook* which is very broad, while the inhibiting factor is that there is still dishonesty, taking a long time to reply to customer messages because they are not read (*Slow Response*)

INTRODUCTION

Currently the business world is experiencing rapid development in terms of sales of gadgets or Cellphone. The development of the digital world has been very fast in recent years. Almost everyone has a gadget or cellphone, in fact each person can carry two to three cellphones at once. This of course means that there are more and more mobile phone manufacturers with various brands.

In the business world, advertising, apart from being an effort to spread thoughts, ideas or messages, is also able to influence someone in the decision-making process to buy and use the product or service. Therefore, marketing strategies play an important role in the success of sales, and in conveying information that needs to be conveyed to the public, there needs to be an approach between sellers and buyers, which is adapted to the situation and conditions of the audience which can be identified by business people by first analyzing existing market opportunities, before determining the target market. The approaches taken are of course steps that become a strategy by carrying out marketing communications as a form of conveying the message that a particular product or service company wants to convey. Marketing communications are also made or created with the main aim of selling.

To achieve a goal, a correct and planned marketing communications strategy is needed because it can be successful in achieving the right target in a timely manner relative fast and not expensive.

The use of social media to achieve targets requires a planned strategy, so that the costs incurred are not wasted, because creative and efficient media is fundamental in the marketing communications strategy that companies need, both in new companies, as a means of cultivating public awareness of products or services offered or as a promotional strategy for a product or service company that is developing its business and of course wants to increase sales. One of platform sale cell phone is Group Facebook Buy and sell Cellphone Cianjur.

Facebook (FB) is still the most popular social media in the world. Based on the Statista report, the social networking media created by Mark Zuckerberg has the highest number of active users compared to other social media, namely 2.9 billion users.

Group Facebook provide platform and a variety of features for Page owners to build interactive and relevant communities between existing and potential customers. Groups are hubs where important conversations continue to thrive between brands and customers, as well as between customers. Groups create a space for customers to become advocates for the business. (Kusnandar, 2022)

Marketing communications is communicating the voice of the company and its brand and is a means by which companies can create dialogue and build relationships with consumers through the messages they want to convey to consumers.

In line with this, Sami and Amri (2017) in a journal entitled Product Marketing Communication Strategy Cellphone in Attracting Buyer Interest which states that a marketing communication strategy with a mix of advertising promotions and personal selling is good in increasing consumer interest. This is also supported by Hambali, Astrid, and Utari (2018) who say that marketing

communication strategies using sales promotion, personal selling, direct selling and advertising very helpful in increasing consumer interest. Based on the background above, researchers are interested in submitting research based on the background of the problem with the title "Product Marketing Communication Strategy Cellphone in Attracting Buyer Interest (Descriptive Study on Social Media Facebook in Group Buy and sell Cellphone Cianjur), to examine the marketing communication strategies carried out by sellers in the group facebook buy and sell cell phone Cianjur. (Nidillah, 2021)

LITERATURE REVIEW

Communication

Communication is generally defined as relationships or activities related to relationship issues or is also defined as an activity of exchanging opinions or thoughts from one person to another person or group of other people (Widjaja, 2000:13).

Marketing Communication Strategy

Shimp in the journal Basic Concepts of Marketing Communication said "Communication is a process where thoughts and understanding are conveyed to several categories such as individuals and individuals or individuals and groups. Meanwhile, marketing is an activity where companies or organizations and even individuals transfer value between themselves and customers." (Suryana, 2015)

Strategy is planning and management to achieve goals. Meanwhile, communication strategy is a combination of communication planning and communication management to achieve a goal. It contains three elements of communication strategy which are usually called STP, namely Segmentation, Targeting, and Positioning.

Marketing Strategy Communication Function

Kotler explained that there is a dual function of communication strategy, both macro (planned multi-media strategy) and micro (single communication medium strategy), namely (1) systematically disseminating informative, persuasive and instructive communication messages to targets to obtain optimal results, and (2) bridging the cultural gap due to the ease of obtaining and ease of operationalization of such powerful mass media, which if left unchecked will destroy cultural values. (Surastuti, 2017)

Communication Tool cellphone (HP)

A Zambrana in a journal entitled The Impact of Communication Technology on the Morality of Islamic Adolescents in 2012 explained that mobile telephones, often called mobile phones (HP) or cellular telephones (cell phones), are electronic telecommunications devices that have the same basic capabilities as conventional fixed line telephones, but can be used anywhere. - anywhere (portable, mobile) and does not need to be connected to a telephone network using a cable. The cellphone is a development in telephone technology which has experienced development from time to time, where the cellphone device can be

used as a mobile device or moved around as a means of communication, conveying information from one party to another becomes more effective and efficient. (Habibi, 2020)

Function Cellphone

It is clear that the biggest function of a cellphone is as a communication tool to stay connected with friends or family, according to its initial function, and apart from the above functions, the cellphone can be useful for increasing knowledge about technological advances and for expanding networks, and the cellphone can also be used as a support business because nowadays businesses can be based online and are easier to access.

Facebook

Facebook is a social networking service in cyberspace that is used to find new friends, old friends and others. Teenagers use Facebook to promote themselves by uploading photos, updating status, and so on. Apart from that, Facebook is used for online business. (Nuryani, 2014)

Group Facebook

Facebook social media is increasingly developing in various aspects, starting from features, access and others. One of these Facebook features is Facebook Groups. A Facebook group is an association of people who use Facebook who gather in a group for a particular purpose. One of these Facebook groups is the Cianjur Mobile Phone Buying and Selling Facebook Group.

BMI theories (Intergrated Marketing Communication)

Shimp (2010) defines IMC as a communication process consisting of planning, creating, integrating and implementing various forms of marketing communications (advertising, sales promotions, publications, events and so on).

IMC Basic Assumptions (Promotion Mix)

1. Advertising

Is all forms of non-personal communication through various mass media such as TV, radio, magazines and newspapers regarding information about companies, products and services or ideas of a known sponsor.

2. Direct Marketing

It is a marketing activity carried out by a company directly to its consumers.

3. Sales Promotion

Marketing activities are carried out by providing incentive value to the sales team, distributors or consumers directly to encourage sales quickly.

4. Public Relation

As well as advertising, publications/public relations is non-personal communication through various mass media such as TV, radio, magazines and newspapers regarding companies, products, services or event sponsors funded directly or indirectly carried out in the form of news release, press conference, articles, films and others.

5. Personal Selling

Is a communication activity carried out directly by the seller to convince potential buyers to buy the product or service offered.

METHODOLOGY

This methodology uses a qualitative research method with a case study approach, used to describe, explain and answer problems with cases and events in this research. The theory used is IMC by Shimp, Kotler & Armstrong (2004). This research sample used a purposive sampling technique. This research informant is considered to be the most knowledgeable about marketing communications in the Buying and Selling Group Cellphone Cianjur. The data collection technique for this research is through observation, interviews and documentation. The validity of the data uses triangulation and data analysis uses Miles & Hubberman.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The Cianjur cellphone buying and selling Facebook group is a forum on Facebook social media for people to gather to sell and buy cellphones, or it can also be called a group that operates in the trade sector.

The Cianjur mobile phone buying and selling Facebook group was founded on April 4 2015, created by Tatan Sutandi and Benu Ibnu. Initially this group was called Buying and Selling Cianjur Cellphones Sukabumi Bandung Bogor, but after several reasons, one of which was too wide a reach, they finally changed the group to the name Buying and Selling Cianjur cellphones, so that it could focus on people who wanted to sell and buy cellphones in the Cianjur area just. In total, 2,549 people have become members of the group.

Table 1. Members of the Cianjur Mobile Phone Buying and Selling Group

No	Name	Age	Information
1	Tatan Sutandi	29	Leader/ Admin
2	Benu Ibnu	31	Moderator
3	Other Members	-	2549 Members

Source: Group Websitefacebook JBHC

3. Public Relation

Figure 3. Public Relation

Utilize the announcement feature to provide information to members, comment on product posts, provide product recommendations if customers are looking for a cellphone according to their needs.

4. Personal Selling

Figure 3. Personal Selling

The marketing method is in language that is easy for customers to understand, providing comments in the form of product offers to sellers' posts who are looking for cellphones.

5. Direct Selling Gambar

Figure 5. Direct Selling

The marketing that is carried out is by always offering new or unused products to people who have made several transactions via direct messages or via WhatsApp, providing comments in the form of products on posts by customers who are looking for a cellphone.

Supporting Factors

Sales supporting factors cell phone of group facebook Buy and sell Cellphone Cianjur can be understood that the seller feels profitable when selling his products in the Group Facebook Buy and sell Cellphone Cianjur. It is explained that the products he posts or publishes can be more easily accessed by potential buyers and the reach of product promotion is wider because there are approximately 2000 members in the group.

Supporting factors for increasing sales cell phone in the Buy and Sell group cell phone Cianjur, namely with quality social media publications, you can convey messages or promotions for products being sold easily to everyone, especially members of the Buy and Sell group Cellphone Cianjur. Apart from that, communication is very easy between sellers and buyers, with the comments feature in posts, and direct messages you can easily get clear product details so that marketing goals are achieved.

With creativity also the seller's promotion in making statements in promoting the product, making potential buyers/customer feel interested in buying products that have been promoted by the seller.

Obstacle Factor

Running a business online is not without obstacles, there are many challenges and obstacles that must be faced. there are several obstacles experienced by sellers, such as communication, because of their nature online, then there is no communication intensive The risk is sometimes slow response or late in answering questions from customer, then because of business online This is currently in demand by many people, so there is a lot of competition or competitors, this requires sellers to better finalize their marketing communication strategies and be able to be more creative in promoting their products. There are still obstacles or obstacles that are felt customer in transactions in the Group Facebook Buy and

sell Cellphone Cianjur, as there is still fraud or dishonesty from sellers in selling their products

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Based on the results of research and discussions that have been presented regarding Marketing Communication Strategy Online Product Cellphone Attracting Buyer Interest has been very good and sales have increased although there are still several obstacles such as responses that sometimes take a long time. This is due to several explanations:

1) In its implementation, the sellers in the Group Facebook Buy and sell cell phone Cianjur has implemented the basic assumptions of the marketing communications strategy, namely advertising, sales promotion, public relation, personal selling, and direct selling. It can be concluded that the implementation of this communication strategy is relevant to the theory used, namely Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC).

2) Supporting factors for increasing seller sales cell phone in the Buy and Sell Group Cellphone Cianjur is social media facebook which can be accessed easily and with sophisticated features can convey messages or posts widely, Quality publications in the Buying and Selling Group Cellphone Cianjur is very good. Can be directly or intensely in communicating with customers via direct messages or whatsapp. Meanwhile, the inhibiting factor is due to direct communication online Sometimes messages sent by customers are not read, which causes problems Slow Respon and make customers wait, then because the sales made are of a nature online However, there are still sellers who are dishonest in the group, which disturbs members' trust. The next inhibiting factor is competitors in business online There are so many that sellers are required to be consistent and more creative.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations, so it is necessary to carry out further research related to the topic of Marketing Communication Strategy Online Product Cell Phone in Attracting Buyers in order to improve this research and add insight to readers.

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